

Implementation of Regional Development Information Systems in Regional Development Planning at Bappeda of Enrekang Regency

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Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the implementation of the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) in Regional Development Planning at Bappeda of Enrekang Regency. The type of research used is a qualitative method with a descriptive approach. Data collection techniques used purposive sampling techniques and data analysis techniques using Nvivo12 Plus software. The results of the study show that the implementation of the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) in terms of policy content and policy environment has been implemented properly, it's just that there are still a number of inputs that need to be considered, such as the need for stages of technical training carried out by the Ministry of Home Affairs or Bappeda of Enrekang Regency, there is a need for relevance between the knowledge capabilities of employees with aspects of tasks that are more relevant as well.

Keywords:- Implementation of Regional Development Information Systems; Development Planning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the implementation of the regional autonomy system in Indonesia, it has encouraged changes in the implementation of Governance and Development. Particularly in development changes, it does not only occur at the central level but also at the city and district levels. The latest regulations governing changes to the administration of regional government and development are Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government and Law Number 9 of 2015 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government. One of the quite fundamental changes in the Administration of Regional Governments mentioned in the regulation is related to regional development. Regional development is said to be the embodiment of the implementation of government affairs which have been partially handed over to the regions as an integral part of National Development. Through this policy, it means that regional governments are given broader authority in managing and regulating government administration affairs. The application of regional autonomy has limited the scope of authority of the central government in terms of managing development at the regional level. So that the Regional Development Planning System which was originally more regional in nature has become more participatory. In addition, changes that are visible in Regional Development

Planning in the current era, namely Regional Development Planning which pay attention to the potential and specific characteristics of each region.

Meanwhile, National Planning is more macro in nature and only provides general directions and targets so that Regional Development can be well coordinated as well as efficient. In order for regional and central development to remain in good synergy, a regulation was made to strengthen the position of Regional Development Planning in Indonesia, namely through Law Number 25 of 2004 concerning the National Development Planning System (SPPN 2004). In Article 31 in Chapter VII of Law Number 25 of 2004 concerning the National Development Planning System, it states that development planning is based on accurate and accountable data/information. Data/information is one of the materials for evaluating the implementation of Regional Development Planning as well as material for determining/formulating policies and planning for regional development. This explanation can be interpreted that in order to be able to prepare good and quality Regional Development Planning, an accurate, accountable and relevant reference data is needed.

Therefore, local governments need a system or application that can become a database center that can be trusted and accurate in presenting data. Also, so that data can be integrated starting from the lowest level of government, namely at the village level. The system in question is a digital-based system that can help facilitate the preparation of Regional Development Planning starting from the stages of preparing plans, establishing plans, controlling the implementation of plans, and evaluating the implementation of plans both in the Regional Long-Term Development Plan (RPJPD),

Regional Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMD) and Regional Government Work Plan (RKPD) [1]. The Regional Development Information System, abbreviated as SIPD, is the management of regional development information, regional financial information, and other regional government information that are interconnected to be utilized in implementing regional development. SIPD is a system that documents, administers, and processes regional development data into information that is presented to the public and as material for decision-making in the framework of planning, implementing, evaluating local government performance [2].

The following figure 1. presents an overview of the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) menu.

Fig. 1: overview of the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) menu

SIPD is a development data management application created, managed and developed by the Director General of Regional Development of the Ministry of Home Affairs [3]. The data in the SIPD application is processed and presented in the form of regional development information with the hope that it can increase understanding, be guided and implemented as a reference for provincial and district/city governments in order to improve the quality of regional development planning, control and evaluation. This SIPD can assist Regional Heads/Heads of Agencies/Heads of Agencies/Heads of Offices/Heads of Work Units in obtaining accurate information and data. The SIPD application is integrated in stages, making it easier for users from the lowest level, namely the village, to manage data on proposals or community complaints that have been discussed, proposal data entered by villages can be arranged based on priority, and villages can also manage proposal data which will later be raised to the sub-district, then will be sent to a higher level, namely the Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA) as the planning manager.

BAPPEDA as a regional planning institution has been confirmed through formal legitimacy, namely Law Number 25 of 2004 concerning the National Development Planning System. BAPPEDA is a regional institution that has received the mandate or mandate to carry out the coordinating function of development planning within the scope of regional government organizations BAPPEDA is a regional planning institution that has been confirmed through formal legitimacy in Law Number 25 of 2004 concerning the National Development Planning System. The Enrekang District Government is one of the regencies that has made preparations for the preparation and development of SIPD data and information. In the 2021 fiscal year, BAPPEDA has started to make adjustments during the transition period, from the old system to the new system, namely SIPD. The activities for preparing the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) are regulated by the Ministry of Home Affairs by issuing Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 8 of

2014 concerning Regional Development Information Systems (SIPD). Based on the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 8 of 2014 concerning Regional Development Information Systems (SIPD), requires a Decree on establishing a Regency/City Working Group Team (Pokja) to Manage Regional Development Information Data, and the Formation of a Regency/City Regional Development Information System Management Team (SIPD).

However, based on data obtained from the Directorate General of Regional Development at the Ministry of Home Affairs, there are 211 regencies where regional government data availability has been integrated with SIPD. Meanwhile, Enrekang Regency was found to be still not integrated with SIPD (e-planning and RKPD). The following is the information presentation through Figure 2:.

Fig. 2: SIPD (e-planning and RKPD)

Source: <https://sipd.go.id/sipdmap/>

From the results of the researcher's initial observations, several problems were found in the Implementation of the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) in Regional Development Planning at the Bappeda of Enrekang Regency, namely not massive coordination between development actors, such as between OPD/SKPD and Bappeda. so that it was constrained in data entry to SIPD, and in the end Enrekang Regency was included in the five regencies in South Sulawesi which were categorized as having Regional Government data that had not been integrated into SIPD. Another problem is the limited proportion of budget allocation and human resources involved in identifying development data, as a result of which the data collection cannot obtain optimal and maximum results. Some previous studies that support the results of the researchers' initial observations, namely [4] with the title Utilization of Regional Information Systems in Supporting Regional Development Planning in Indonesia, found several problems that occurred such as weak understanding, coordination and commitment of local governments in using SIPD as a basis for preparing and evaluation of regional planning/legal database; the data is still partial in the regions so that it varies and the conditions for filling in the SIPD data elements are incomplete and not updated; Limited professional human resources; Infrastructure limitations; and budget limitations.

Furthermore, from the results of research by [5] with the title Implementation of Regional Development Information Systems (SIPD) in Improving Regional Development Coordination, Studies on the Implementation of SIPD in BAPPEDA Bengkulu City. The results of his research stated that even though the SIPD Implementation at BAPPEDA Bengkulu City was in accordance with applicable regulations. However, there are still some obstacles, such as the lack of awareness of SIPD executors about the implementation of SIPD which can be seen from the level of filling out of SIPD data in the city of Bengkulu. In addition, the implementing regulations related to administrative sanctions for the person in charge of SIPD have not been maximized to increase the level of compliance in filling in data.

In addition, [2] in his research on the application of SIPD at the Regional Development Planning Agency of Indragiri Hilir Regency, found results that based on analysis with the theory of Support, Capacity, and Value the application of SIPD was quite good, but the data elements were not fully met, this was due to due to inadequate human resources in terms of data input, where each regional government organization operator has multiple positions as operator in other systems. Ideally, in the development planning process accompanied by complete and comprehensive data, it is an important point for the success of regional development. Therefore, a valid and measurable database and information is needed. So, if the input data is inaccurate, the resulting development plan will not solve the existing problems. Thus, as an important point in the planning input stage, valid, updated and accountable data and information bases are needed as well as analysis of regional development that can describe the condition of the region as a whole [6]. So that it is hoped that the output of regional development planning in the form of development plan documents is able to answer development problems and achieve development targets [7]. The purpose of this study was to determine the Implementation of the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) in Regional Development Planning at the Bappeda of Enrekang Regency.

II. METHODS

This type of research uses qualitative methods [8] qualitative research methods try to find the meaning of a phenomenon that comes from the views of the participants. Regional Development Information System (SIPD) in Regional Development Planning at Bappeda Enrekang Regency. Interviews were used with structured methods on research objects and documentation techniques with literature reviews, journals, related regulations, statistical data, previous research and similar research. This research was analyzed using Nvivo12 Plus software, namely by analyzing and describing the Implementation of Regional Development Information Systems (SIPD) in Regional Development Planning at Bappeda Enrekang Regency. The research data that has been collected through interviews is processed through Nvivo, the interview data is matched with

predetermined research indicators. The coding process is adapted to the theory that has been used. Classifying data as a process of translating data coding, classifying the classification process using Nvivo crosstabulation, crosstabulation as a process of comparing each data. The last stage in the nvivo analysis process is the display of data in the form of graphs and tables, this analysis model in Nvivo is called the five-step analysis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Implementation of the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) in Regional Development Planning at Bappeda of Enrekang Regency

Fig. 3: SIPD Program Data

Source: Admin of Regional Devices, 2019

In implementing a policy there are four aspects that must be considered, namely: (1) Who is involved in the implementation; (2) The nature of the administrative process; (3) Compliance with a policy; and (4) Effect or impact of implementation [10]. This view shows that policy implementation is a dynamic process that involves continuous efforts to achieve what leads to the placement of a program into the desired decision goals. The successful implementation of a public policy can be measured from the process of achieving the final results (outcomes), namely whether or not the objectives to be achieved are achieved. The public policy implementation approach proposed by Grindle is known as "implementation as a political and administrative process". Where the measurement of the success of the implementation of the policy is seen from two things, namely the content of the policy, including, first, the interest that influences (interest effected). Second, Type of Benefits, Third, Degree of change to be achieved (Extent Of Change Envision), Fourth, Location of decision making (Site Of Decision Making), Fifth, Implementation of the program (Program Implementer), Sixth, Resources used (Resources Committed). Then the implementation environment (Context OI implementation), includes: Power, interests and strategies of the actors involved (Power, Interest, and Strategy of Actor Involved),

Characteristics of institutions and regimes in power (Institution and Regime Characteristics), Level of compliance and response from implementers (Compliance and Responsiveness) [11].

B. Policy Content

➤ Target Group Interests

The target group is a group of people or organizations in society who will receive goods and services or whose behavior will be influenced by policies. Policy implementation depends on policy implementers (implementors) and target groups (target groups). Implementers must have the capability, competence, commitment and consistency to implement a policy in accordance with the directions of policy makers. In addition, an educated and relatively homogeneous target group will more easily accept a policy than a closed, traditional and heterogeneous group. Furthermore, the target group which is a large part of the population will also make it more difficult for successful implementation. The implementation of a government system that uses (electronic) technology is to utilize information and communication technology in the framework of developing services for the community which is expected as a form of encouragement (Presidential Regulation, 2018). The Regional Government Information System (SIPD) is very well implemented. This system was implemented to encourage the implementation of effective, innovative and quality information by activating the substance of Permendagri Number 70 of 2019 concerning Regional Government Information Systems (Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs, 2019), in every district/city government, especially in Bapedda Enrekang Regency.

In accordance with the Regulation of Minister of Home Affairs Number 98 of 2018 Concerning Regional Development Information Systems, article 3, which reads "Local Governments carry out mapping, collection, filling, validation, and evaluation of government data. Regions use Electronic Data/E-Database applications" (Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs, 2018). So almost all regional apparatuses in Indonesia have been transformed from working manually to using electronics in carrying out their duties. The same is the case with the use and implementation of SIPD at Bapedda Enrekang Regency. Because it is clear legally and SOPs are applied in an effort to streamline work.

From the results of the interview above and the source of the existing regulations, based on this, the conclusion is that the impact and benefits of SIPD are not only felt by Bapedda Enrekang Regency, but this is also felt by OPD in Enrekang Regency in managing planning and budgeting. This makes it easier for regional apparatus and apparatus to coordinate with each other and access remotely so as to save time and be effective in finalizing development documents.

➤ Benefit Type

At this point the content of the policy seeks to show or explain that in a policy there must be several types of benefits that show a positive impact. Program implementation can be said to be successful if the program has the desired impact. A program may be viewed from a process standpoint, but may fail when viewed from what is produced. The criteria for measuring implementation success are based on three aspects, namely (1) the level of bureaucratic compliance with the bureaucracy above it or the level of bureaucracy as stipulated in the law; (2) there is a smooth routine and there are no problems; (3) the desired implementation and impact or benefits of all existing programs are directed [12]. Based on this theory it can be said that the success of a program implemented is not seen only in terms of the implementation of the program if only seen from the process, but also must be seen from the benefits arising from the program.

Based on the theoretical basis and sources from interview informants regarding the types of benefits from SIPD implementation, it can be concluded that the results and impacts obtained from a policy are very important to measure the success or failure of a policy so that it can become material in formulating a policy. Regarding the benefits of SIPD at Bapedda, Enrekang Regency, it is considered that it has been running well, because its benefits and uses have been felt by the relevant regional apparatus and apparatus. This will certainly support the performance and productivity of government institutions to realize the desired development. This is based on the alignment of programs in OPD that are in accordance with existing programs in the region. So that there are no more development programs that are not in line with what is the vision of the region.

➤ Desired Degree of Change

Of course, every policy has a target to be and want to achieve. The content of the policy to be explained must have a clear scale. The extent to which the change is desired from the existence of a policy. The degree of change to be achieved shows how much change you want or want to achieve through the implementation of a policy. If referring to the statement put forward by [12] said that there are 3 elements in seeing the success of policy implementation, (a). The compliance perspective that measures the implementation of the compliance of the implementing apparatus. (b). The success of implementation is measured by the smoothness of the routine and the absence of problems, and (c). Successful implementation leads to satisfactory performance for all parties, especially the program beneficiary group.

Based on the results of the interviews conducted above, it can be concluded that the changes that occurred in the development planning stages in Enrekang Regency had a very positive impact on data collection from various OPDs. Problems related to planning documents and inconsistencies in development programs can be minimized. So that the transformation of services from a manual system to an IT

system has been going well. So that it can be said that the SIPD policy in development planning has been going well.

Fig. 4: Phased Schedule Input Process

Source: (Regional Device Admin, 2019)

The process of changing services has become a public demand and there are clear regulations from the central government down to the regional governments to maximize performance and provide satisfaction to the public in services. This will not happen without adequate policies and competent apparatus in running the government system. So actually, the policy was designed and issued to be able to solve good problems and make it easier for officials and even the community to give and get their rights and obligations as citizens in realizing development according to the UN target in 2030 [13].

According to the results of the interviews conveyed by the informants above, it can be concluded that in the desired stages of change from the SIPD policy it is as expected. This is based on what was the obstacle prior to the implementation of this SIPD, the apparatus in the Enrekang Regency Bapedda. regional users and devices in Enrekang district. This greatly facilitates the apparatus in carrying out their duties and functions in processing data and preparing the data needed in the development planning that will be carried out. This is very effective because regional apparatuses who will send their development planning documents to their respective OPDs do not need to take up more time and money, because this can already be done by sending documents to the SIPD user in Bapedda Enrekang Regency.

➤ Location of decision making

Decision making in a policy plays an important role in the implementation of a policy, whether the location of a program is appropriate or not. Making a decision in a policy plays an important role in implementing a policy, therefore in this section it must be explained where the decision making of a policy will be implemented. At least in analyzing decision making there are four types of processes: individual, group, organizational, and cooperative [14]. Decision making can be thought of as a cognitive process that results in selecting a course of action from several alternative scenarios. Decision-

making problems range from everyday decisions, such as choosing an itinerary to go from one place to another, to more complex decisions involving large numbers of individuals, associations, or socio-economic groups. Complex decisions generally require the development of formal methods for dealing with them. Several methods have been proposed in the literature, including cost-benefit analysis, statistical techniques, evolutionary algorithms and multicriteria analysis. Majority of decision-making methods assume a single decision maker for simplicity, whereas real-world problems require decisions to naturally imply multiple decision makers with conflicting goals and different value systems [15].

Based on the theoretical statements and the results of interviews with existing informants, it can be concluded that the decentralization process in the SIPD policy has been running from the center to the Bapedda of Enrekang Regency. In general, those who have authority in decision-making are the parties from the Ministry of Home Affairs who are the subject of this SIPD policy to be carried out by government agencies, including in this case the Bapedda of Enrekang Regency as the implementer.

➤ Program Executor

In carrying out a policy or program, it must be supported by the existence of competent and capable policy implementers. For the success of a policy, whether a policy has specified the implementor in detail. In implementing a policy or program, it must be supported by the existence of competent and capable policy implementers for the success of a policy. In the process of implementing a program, it can actually be successful, less successful, or fail altogether when viewed from the form of the results achieved or outcomes. Because in this process, various elements can be seen whose influence supports or hinders the achievement of program goals.

In accordance with the juridical basis and what was conveyed by informants in the interviews conducted, the authors conclude that the process of implementing the SIPD program at Bapedda Enrekang Regency has been going well. However, it is still constrained by inadequate systems and networks so that it can disrupt the performance of regional apparatus in development planning. Then the SIPD application is still considered not to meet the needs of Bapedda Enrekang Regency because there are no features related to the process of monitoring and evaluating development programs. So that this SIPD is considered not yet transparent in the development evaluation and monitoring process. Finally, related to the implementation of the program, it is considered that they have not been optimal in providing provisioning in terms of technical training to support the performance of SIPD operators.

IV. RESOURCE

A program supported by adequate resources. The implementation of a policy must also be supported by adequate resources with the aim that the implementation can run well. management is the science and art of managing the process of utilizing human resources and other sources effectively and efficiently to achieve a goal [16]. Management is almost the same as management, so the process of managing human resources cannot be separated from the process of managing human resources in an organization, both on the scale of government and private agencies. So, the conclusion from the above is that in the process of achieving goals, of course there are several components that need attention. Such as human resources and other resources. In order for this resource to run optimally, it must be considered and managed properly. What is a need must be given in order to achieve the goal? So, to increase resources, education and training are needed, this is a form of activity in increasing competence and is an integral part of human resource management. In the implementation of education and training, it is necessary to have effective management and proper coordination between employees or the organizing committee regarding the training that will be carried out. So that it can produce human resources that are reliable and have certain competencies according to organizational needs [17].

Therefore, to increase resources, especially human resources, quality improvement is needed so that they are able to keep up with societal and global demands. Especially in the use of electronics and compensation for apparatus in order to improve their performance. In implementing policies, the most important thing in implementing these policies is resources, such as human resources and other resources. Without resources, the process of implementing the policy will run in place, even if human resources are available but are not equipped with high capabilities, then this will become a problem that can affect the performance of implementing the policy. Therefore, it is important to clarify the division of jobs and improve the quality of employees.

Based on the above and the interviews conducted, the authors conclude that the stages of job distribution and compensation for implementing the policy already exist and are running, but when there are problems in the policy or technical matters of the application, this will be delegated to the Ministry of Home Affairs. On the basis of the theory put forward previously as well as existing regulations and sources from informants. So, the authors conclude that in the implementation of this SIPD they already have their respective jobs or tasks at the Bapedda Enrekang Regency level. The budget for the implementation of the SIPD comes from Bapedda, but is not presented in a transparent manner. Then what is most important in this implementation in terms of resources is that there is no special training held either from the Ministry of Home Affairs or the Regional Government itself so that when there are problems related to the

implementation of this SIPD, you don't have to wait for confirmation from the Ministry of Home Affairs.

V. CONCLUSION

Policy Contents; (1) Interests of the Target Group, the target group (target group) is a group of people or organizations in society who will receive goods and services or whose behavior will be influenced by policies. (2) Types of Benefits, Policy content seeks to show or explain that in a policy there must be several types of benefits that show a positive impact. (3) The desired degree of change, the degree of change to be achieved shows how much change one wants or wants to achieve through the implementation of a policy; (4) The location of decision making, related to decision making in the implementation of SIPD is still considered centralized because it must follow what is the direction of the Ministry of Home Affairs; (5) Program executors, in implementing the SIPD Implementation program, are part of Bapedda Enrekang Regency itself who are users, and OPD is one of the beneficiaries of this SIPD program, while the Ministry is considered to only provide outreach at the beginning and is not sustainable; (6) Resources, in terms of resources, as implementers of the SIPD policy, the Ministry and Bapedda of Enrekang Regency are considered not to be maximized to increase the potential of their apparatus because the findings obtained by the authors are that before the implementation of this SIPD was carried out, no stages of technical training were carried out for users or admins in Enrekang Regency and OPD in Enrekang Regency.

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